

Signs of Gay Life in the 24th Century: homosexuality in *Star Trek* Fan Films.

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ABSTRACT.- From its inception, *Star Trek* has generated a very active fan community which may well have given the fullest measure of the fandom phenomenon as we know it. Since the appearance of the first thematic fanzine, *Spockanalia* (1967), fan fiction has become a regular staple of the fandom grown around the TV series created by Gene Roddenberry. Slash fiction is a variety of fan fiction devoted to exploring homosexual relationships between the main characters of the series, above all that between Captain Kirk and Mr. Spock. Nowadays, fan films, as direct inheritors of the traditional fan fiction, explore never before revealed homosexual relationships within the *Star Trek* universe, with such outstanding examples as the 'Blood and Fire' episode of *Star Trek: Phase II*, from a rejected script originally written for *Star Trek: The Next Generation*, or *Star Trek: The Hidden Frontier*, both protagonized by homosexual characters.

Keywords: Star Trek, Fan films, Fandom, Songvid, Gay Fandom.

Introduction

'In more than four decades Star Trek [...] has broken through many barriers, such as being the first to have an interracial kiss (between William Shatner and Nichelle Nichols) on broadcast television, as well as touting the values of peace and tolerance for all. Yet the series has refused to address forthrightly the topic of homosexuality.'

- AfterElton, *Star Trek's Forbidden Gay Frontier*, April 20, 2006.

'I was born that way. I have had those feelings... those longings... all my life. It is not unnatural.

I am not sick because I feel this way. I do not need to be helped, and I do not need to be cured.

What I do need -- what all of those like me need -- is your understanding and your compassion.'

- Soren, *The Outcast, Star Trek. The Next Generation*

The first issue that may arise after reading the title of this paper is why I have chosen to study *Star Trek*; the answer is that Gene Roddenberry's series has remained active since

the late sixties until now in the form of its different franchises and film adaptations. Also, because, despite not being the first media fandom historically, the community of *Star Trek* followers was the first important media fandom whose members were able to affect the destiny of their object of devotion. Namely, an avalanche of letters sent by those fans convinced the TV executives to keep the original series running for at least one more season. The activity of this group of fans, who would become the model for all successive media fandoms, included the publication of *Spockanalia*, the first fanzine dedicated to a TV show. Besides *Star Trek* trivia, *Spockanalia* also offered the first examples of fan fiction inspired by this series: ‘Ruth Berman, who was later to put out her own *Star Trek* fanzine, wrote the concluding story, ‘Star Drek’. Another item of interest in the first issue of *Spockanalia* was ‘The Territory of Rigel’ a Ni Var poem by Dorothy Jones’ (Verba, 2003, p.1). The described contents reflect both the fans’ intention to produce artistic material based on the series and the importance of women in the formation of media fandom.

Despite being a science fiction series, the author permits himself to satirize ‘contemporary society through tales of the fantastic, challenging a system of production which allowed little space for personal expression or social commentary’ (Jenkins, 1995, p.185). However, the strength of this series lies in giving a positive picture of humankind by virtue of ‘a recurrent myth running through *Star Trek* [which] is the belief that technological progress, the creation of new systems of communication and transportation, the mastery of disease and starvation through scientific advances, the expansion into space, had led to a resolution of the sources of human conflict’ (Jenkins, 1995, p.178).

This paper revolves around a series whose narrative deals with the harmony among races and their different customs, but takes no notice of homosexual relationships between characters or, at best, portrays them as mere anecdotes. *Star Trek* can be defined as a heterocentric society where ‘heterosexuality is the universal norm by which everyone’s experience can be understood. Heterocentrism renders lesbian and gay experience invisible’ (Tyson, 2006, p.320-321), which is a vital issue to consider in order to understand the *Star Trek* universe and its stereotypes. These stereotypes are very important due to the strong fan identification with ‘the programs, the characters, the producers and their ideological conceptions, even when they feel strong frustration

with the failure of the producers to create stories they would like to see told' (Jenkins, 2006, p.111). This leads to a wide variety of interpretations: 'Those different interpretations of the text reflect the primary generic diversity and ideological contradictions of the broadcast narratives as well as the different needs and desires which draw these different populations to the same program' (Jenkins, 1995, p.192), and leads to what Jenkins called resistant reading, 'a source of a collective identity and mutual support' (Jenkins, 2006, p.112).

Even though the texts which originate the fan films are heterocentric, gay characters and their relationships are as important as heterosexual ones in a significant number of productions made by fans of the franchise.

Sexuality in the *Star Trek* franchise

Star Trek, as created by Gene Roddenberry, is based on the principle of equality between people regardless of their race or origin. Thus, from the beginning, in the original series there are leading characters that do not fit the standards of the era: namely, middle-aged Anglo-Saxon white men. That canon of the 1960s started to fade with the inclusion of Uhura, a woman of African origin played by Nichelle Nichols, and Sulu, an Asian man played by George Takei, in the Enterprise starship crew. This series also broke new ground when it showed the first interracial kiss on American television, notably in the episode *Plato's Stepchildren*, aired on November 22, 1968. One of Gene Roddenberry's main intentions was to use 'the crew as a microcosm for reflecting larger social transformations' (Jenkins, 1995, p.180)

Just as the franchise illustrates the integration of people from different social and racial backgrounds, the different species of extraterrestrial origin embody the various facets of human personality, such as: violence in Klingon; irascibility in Andorians; or rationality in Vulcans. But, despite the TV show's exemplarity in the aforementioned topics, a similarly open-minded treatment of sexuality is yet to come. It is heteronormativity that characterizes sexuality in the *Star Trek* universe, that is, the discrimination of any homosexual relationship while equating heterosexuality with normality. From beginning to end, all of the relationships between the main characters displayed in the series show that sexual complementarity is only possible between a man and a woman.

Heteronormativity as IDIC sexual issue

In the fictional universe of *Star Trek*, Infinite Diversity in Infinite Combinations (IDIC) is a Vulcan saying that serves to define the series' idiosyncrasy with regard to tolerance and respect between people from different worlds. However, the application of this concept concerning sexual relations throughout the franchise is crushed under the weight of heteronormativity. Unlike anything you would expect from applying the philosophy of IDIC to sex, all through the series, the main characters venture only into heterosexual relationships.

In the original series there are examples of strictly heterosexual relationships which could qualify as 'dead girlfriend of the week' instances, since they adhere to the following type of plot: on the course of a mission in which the Enterprise crew participates, some of its male members meets a woman and falls in love with her, but, at the end of the episode, she dies or has to leave. The archetypal example of this kind of relationship is episode *The City on the Edge Forever*, aired on April 6, 1967, in which Kirk has to let his beloved die so as not to interfere with the space-time continuum. Over time, the arrival of new franchises and the use of story arcs led to the formation of more enduring monogamous relationships, such as the interspecies couples formed by Jadzia Dax (Female-Trill) and Worf (Male-Klingon) in *Star Trek: Deep Space Nine* (Paramount Television, 1993-1999); by B'Elana Torres (Female –half human, half klingon) and Tom Paris (Male-Human) on *Star Trek: Voyager* (Paramount Television, 1995-2001); or Tucker (Male-Human) and T'Pol (Female-Vulcan) in *Enterprise* (Paramount Television, 2001-2005).

Furthermore, in this universe there are polygamy and poliamory, both represented in the *Enterprise* series character Dr. Phlox, from the planet Denobulan, where a male can be married to many females, like in the traditional Islamic conception of marriage, though in this case these wives can also be married to other men, which is poliamory. At the other extreme, there are diverse grades of celibacy: the absolute one of the Deltans in the first film adaptation of the galactic saga, *Star Trek: The Motion Picture* (Robert Wise, 1979); also, celibacy as a way of life for the religious Bajorans in *Deep Space Nine*; and the limited celibacy of Vulcans, whose males experience the so called Pon

Farr every seven years, a fever which makes them behave violently and eventually kills them unless they mate with the females they were mentally bonded to.

Other types of sexual relationships within the *Star Trek* universe go several steps beyond interraciality, since they portray procreation as a result of sex between characters from different planets, with the foremost example of the popular Mr. Spock, the child of a human mother and a Vulcan father, a crossbreed as one of the main characters of a TV show in the mid-twentieth century America; or the half-human/half-Betazoid officer Deanna Troi in *The Next Generation* (Paramount Television, 1987-1994). Then, some extraterrestrial races' process of reproduction involves the participation of a third gender besides male and female, as seen in the episode *Cogenitor* from the *Enterprise* series. And, perhaps, the most controversial installment of the *Star Trek* saga because of its relatively overt treatment of apparent homosexuality is *The Next Generation* chapter *The Outcast* which presents an androgynous society in which opting for one determinate gender identity is considered a dysfunction.

Star Trek Franchise: No Signs of Gay Life in the 24th Century

As we saw earlier, *Star Trek* features a wide range of people of all races, both terrestrial and extraterrestrial, in order to promote understanding and solidarity between different worlds. But, regarding sex, there is an aspect which is omitted by default all along the franchise, both in movies and in TV series: homosexuality. This absence can be understood in two divergent ways: one, homosexuality is still frowned upon in the *Star Trek* universe, despite the social advances shown in the series; or, two, homosexuality has become so common that there is no need to show it. After Gene Roddenberry's death, executive producer Rick Berman stated 'we do not see heterosexual couples holding hands on the show, so it would be somewhat dishonest of us to see two gay men or lesbians holding hands' (quoted on Ricci, 2006). That statement was refuted by Michael Roeder, who produced a list of the number of times the TV series explicitly shows manifestations of heterosexuality in comparison with other kinds of sexual relationships: as we have seen so far, the vast majority of the relationships portrayed in the series are heterosexual. In 1991, Roddenberry had announced to *The Advocate* magazine: 'In the fifth season of *Star Trek: the Next Generation*, viewers will see more of shipboard life in some episodes, which will, among other things, include gay crew

members in day-to-day circumstances' (Clark, 1991). However his decease a few months later prevented his promises from becoming reality and, although during Berman's tenure some episodes have happened to have a queer backdrop, the gay followers of the series have felt uneasy about them.

Among those episodes are: from *The Next Generation*, *The Offspring* (aired 12 March 1990), *The Host* (aired on 13 May 1991), *The Outcast* (aired on 16 March 1992) and *Blood & Fire*, which did not pass the script stage; from *Deep Space Nine*, the episodes *Rejoined* (aired 30 October 1995) and *The Emperor's New Cloak* (aired 3 February 1999).

In the *The Offspring*, Data, the *The Next Generation* android, built another android with female aspect called Lal. At a certain point in the episode, Guinan, played by Whoopi Goldberg, tries to explain to the female-looking android what love is:

According to the script, Guinan was supposed to start telling Lal, 'When a man and a woman are in love ...!' and in the background, there would be men and women sitting at tables, holding hands," Arnold says. 'But Whoopi refused to say that. She said, 'This show is beyond that. It should be 'When two people are in love.' And so it was decided on set that one of the tables in the background should have two men holding hands -- or two women, or whatever. But someone ran to a phone and made a call to the production office and that was nixed. [Producer] David Livingston came down and made sure that didn't happen. (Sinclair, 2003)

However, the discourse presented in *The Offspring* goes beyond the controversy caused by a sentence, since it reveals the theory of Donna Haraway in her *Cyborg Manifesto*: the gender-sex dilemma is purely a social and historical construct. In consonance with Haraway's thesis, every decision Lal makes in *The Offspring* is biased by these social and historical contexts.

In *The Host*, Dr. Beverly Crusher falls in love with Odan, a male Trill, whose body hosts a parasite which constitutes his true personality. When the parasite is transplanted to a female body after the host body has died in an accident, Beverly rejects the new Odan, either because they both have same-sex physiques or because, as she says, human beings are not used to changes.

After Roddenberry's death, the *Star Trek: The Next Generation* queer episode *par excellence* should be *The Outcast*, in which an androgynous race whose members lack a determinate sex first discriminate and then re-educate those who prefer to be either female or male. During the episode, Riker, the second-in-command played by Jonathan Frakes, falls in love with Soren, an inhabitant of this planet that feels inclined toward femininity. An excerpt from Soren's dialogue exposes a typical feeling of many real-life people in the 1980s:

I must be careful not to reveal myself... On our world these feelings are forbidden. Those who are discovered are shamed and ridiculed. Only by undergoing psychotectic therapy and having all elements of gender eliminated can they become accepted into society again... Those of us who have these urges live secret, guarded lives. We seek each other out... always hiding, always terrified of being discovered... I've known I was different all my life. But I didn't understand how or why until I was older.

On the other hand, there was a notorious screenplay by David Gerrold which was never shot due to its controversial content. Gerrold had also penned the episode which may be the most popular one of the classic series *The Trouble with Tribbles* (aired 29 December 1967), where Dr. McCoy refers to a species of furry animals which reproduce at an alarmingly fast rate as bisexual, though he actually means hermaphrodites. Years later, Gerrold designed the *Blood & Fire* story as a metaphor for love and AIDS in the gay community of the mid-'80s, a disease that was a plague on this community, 'at the end of the decade a generation of men died from it, six times the number of American soldiers killed in the Vietnam War'(Tyson, 2006, p.331). I will discuss this story later because the unused script was eventually developed into a fan film.

The most outstanding homosexual references in *Deep Space Nine* correspond to the aforementioned episodes *Rejoined* and *The Emperor's New Cloak*, both of which have to do with women-kissing-women, but without actually transgressing the heteronormative order established in *Star Trek*. In *Rejoined*, it is a kiss between two Trill hosts, a species seen before in the episode *The Host*, involving parasites that travel from one host body to another keeping their personalities. In this case, two Trills who had previously had a romantic relationship while inhabiting bodies of different genders meet again, but this time they are both in female bodies. They kiss, but, in the end, they return to their heteronormatively 'normal' lives. In *The Emperor's New Cloak*, the

Bajoran character Kira Nerys kisses other women, though, interestingly, this story does not take place in the formal *Star Trek* universe, but in what is known as a 'mirror universe' which shows the dark sides of the characters.

To sum up, two different factors define the representation of homosexuality in the *Star Trek* universe: the first one is the rejection of same-sex relationships, since they are relegated to mostly secondary alien characters or set in alternative universes; secondly, in the 1980s, when AIDS was regarded as a plague within the gay community, there were anachronistic metaphors which dealt with the disease.

Gay Fandom

Henry Jenkins, who has explored in depth the conflict between gay fandom and the producers of the franchise, suggests that the fact that the *Blood & Fire* story did not pass the script stage led to an escalation in the tactics of this fandom because:

Copies of the script have circulated informally among, Gaylaxians and other fans. 'Blood and Fire' became part of the fan community's understanding of the program history and was a key factor for motivating the Gaylaxians to adopt more aggressive strategies in lobbying for their cause (Jenkins, 2006, p.100)

Collectives like the Gaylaxians use techniques such as bulk mailing of letters and emails to pressure the producers of the series, just as another group of fans of *Star Trek* series had managed to keep the original series running for another season years before. The motivations of these groups are:

Fictional motivation- This desire to picture a positive future in which sexual barriers don't exist any longer (just like racism and sexism have been eliminated too), to an extent that has not yet been accomplished today. In other words, whenever homosexuality is depicted on *Star Trek*, it should be a non-issue. It should not be anything like a gay couple on a starship who need to keep their relationship secret from a homophobic captain. No one in Starfleet is supposed to be that reactionary.

Real-world motivation- The second motivation is the integrative and statistically correct representation in *Star Trek* of gay, lesbian and bisexual fans just like every national or racial group of today's world should have its place. In other words, even if there are certain reasons and good fictional explanations why a group shouldn't exist or shouldn't be visible in the future, *Star Trek* should be impartial and include them nonetheless. (Schneider, 2008)

These reasons are the basis of associations such as the Gaylactic Network, a group formed in 1986 that assembles 12 previous groups whose claims are focused on the representation of gays in television and specifically in fantasy films and television series. Among its goals, the Gaylactic Network promotes the presence of lesbian, gay, bisexual and transgender elements within Science Fiction, Fantasy and Horror fiction and within fandom itself in a positive way. Its members define themselves as ‘an alliance of autonomous organizations and individuals bound together by a common interest in the science fiction, fantasy, horror genres and related issues that concern gay men, lesbians, Bisexuals, Transgendered people and their friends’(Gaylactyc Network Website). But being a part of the Gaylactyc Network neither implies nor requires a specific gender or sexual orientation. So, what is special about this kind of networks? Obviously, not the sexual orientation of members, but how they read and interpret texts, and what they demand from them.

The most common strategy of these groups is the massive letter-writing campaigns demanding the introduction of regular gay characters in the series to the powers-that-be. In this sense, the Voyager Visibility Project campaigns for a gay character in the series are exemplary:

The Voyager Visibility Project is an organization of gay and lesbian science fiction fans, writers and media activists, sponsored by the San Francisco Bay Area Chapter of the Gay & Lesbian Alliance Against Defamation, which recently launched an internet-based petition drive demanding that Star Trek producers Rich Berman, Jeri Taylor and Michael Pillar live up to Gene Roddenberry's August 1991 statement that gay and lesbian crewmembers would begin appearing on Star Trek: The Next Generation in the fall of that year. (Perkins, 1996)

This association of Star Trek fans was the most active one along with the USS Harvey Milk, and co-sponsored by GLAAD (Gay and Lesbian Alliance Against Defamation), with its period of greatest activity during the broadcast of *Star Trek: Voyager* (Paramount Television, 1995-2001). At the beginning of the fourth season, the rumor of the introduction of a gay character in the person of Seven of Nine, a human character with a high percentage of his body had been replaced by robotic parts, provoked a campaign of letters to the producers of the series. The Voyager Visibility Project asked the producers of the show to add a positive on-going gay or lesbian character to the cast of *Star Trek: Voyager* under the condition that it should be a regular human being. They requested that humanity because in the rare cases the homosexual issue has been

addressed it had always been done with non human characters whose cultures were totally different from those of earth, producing some strangeness with respect to homosexuality, the following excerpt illustrates the efforts of these groups:

Please! You portray a gay or lesbian character exactly the same way you portray a straight character. You have them talk about their current love interest or partner and the things they do together, you have them mention their first anniversary or recall their first date, you have them express concern when the person they care about is in danger, you show them making a date or expressing interest in a potential partner by asking another crew member whether that person is attached and what that person's orientation is, you show them holding hands in the mess, discussing their day over dinner in their shared quarters, embracing, and -- gasp-- perhaps kissing each other on the shoulder, the head, the cheek or even the lips ... just like heterosexuals!! (From a letter to Jerry Taylor, executive producer of *Star Trek: Voyager*)

At the end of the letter, we can find the other side of this fight, the struggle for the positive depiction of a human gay character:

The introduction of a positive, ongoing gay or lesbian character on *Star Trek Voyager* or *Deep Space Nine* (where you have certainly made some interesting and positive statements regarding gender) will still be a milestone” (*idem*)

When a group of fans feel totally disappointed because the representation of themselves in a TV show, in this case *Star Trek*, provokes a situation where these groups generate their own content, Jenkins says about this:

Resistant reading can sustain the Gaylaxians' own activism, can become a source of collective identity and mutual support, but precisely because its a subcultural activity that is denied public visibility, resistant reading cannot change the political agenda, cannot challenge other constructions of gay identity, and cannot have an impact on the ways people outside of the group think about the issues that matter to the Gaylaxians, Slash, or K/S fiction, represents a long-standing tradition in the women's fan-writing community that poses ways of constructing homoerotic fantasies employing the series characters (Jenkins, 2006, p.111)

The author points to two defining characteristics of media fandom: on one hand, resistance, the ability to organize in order to demand things from the producers of TV series; and secondly, the creation of new texts from others –which Gerard Genette

called hypotexts- which are slowly creating a new canon within the boundaries of fandom.

***Star Trek* Fan Films, a Queer Canonical and Fanonical Representation**

A fan film can be defined as a non-profit amateur audiovisual production whose central theme is some media phenomenon of which the producers are fans. M.E. Russell published a definition of fan film in the digital edition of the *Weekly Standard* in May 2004:

‘Fan Films’ are works that steal characters and situations from a licensed movie franchise without permission. (It will surprise no one that the most-purloined franchises are *Star Wars* and *Star Trek*.) They are usually, but not always, shot by amateurs. The films themselves--which made the bootleg rounds at conventions before the Internet--are now distributed for free online, many of them at sites such as FanFilms.com and [iFilm](#). The fan-filmmaker can't profit from his work, because he's usually already stretching the notion of fair use to the limits. This is a critical point: A fan film may occasionally make fun, but it's a different animal from satire. (Russell, 2004)

This definition highlights the issue of intellectual property rights on the characters. The lack of ownership of the rights on these franchises prevents the fan film producers from economically profiting from their productions.

Some of these fan films are conceived as parts of an expanded version of the source universe, from which the characters and the situations are taken and which constitutes the canon of the series. The canon consists of all the defining parameters of a fictional universe, which in most cases are fixed by the holders of the intellectual property. Their control extends to the licenses, though not all licenses contribute to the canonical, but to the expanded universe instead. On the other hand, there is the fanon, those aspects of the original products that are repeated once and again in the fandom productions: fan fiction, fan art or fan films.

I will show how fan films portray homosexuality taking into account the implementation of these two concepts: canon and fanon. The first batch of productions includes the *Blood and Fire-Part 1* episode of the series of fan films *Star Trek: Phase II*

as well as the emergence of gays as regular characters in the series *Star Trek: Hidden Frontier*. Both series attempt to demonstrate that homosexual relationships exist in the original series in a canonical context with respect to the franchise. Then, in function of the fanon, I will use *Closer* from Tjones & Killa to see how the Kirk/Spock relationship is exploited to the maximum.

Canonical Homosexuality in *Star Trek* Fan Films

Star Trek: Phase II was created at the end of the last century by James Cawley and Jack Marshall as an attempt to explore the two last years of the Enterprise mission which were left untold after the original series was prematurely cancelled. In the moment *Star Trek: New Voyages* was born, it was a venturesome enterprise indeed, since it recovered some characters that viewers identified very strongly with the actors who had played them in the classic series. Cawley always plays the role of Kirk, but other regular characters - including Spock, Sulu and Uhura - have been played by more than one actor each throughout this series of fan films.

In order to minimize the impact due to the change of actors, Cawley and Marshall pushed hard to keep the aesthetics of the original series of the sixties, from the costumes to the camera shots to the credit titles to the music. Their intention was that every episode they produced could pass as one from the original series, as long as they were able 'to show the details of Star Trek canon in their props and costumes' (Anderton, 2006). At the same time, their post-production was up to the standards of any contemporary audiovisual product. CBS and Paramount Pictures, the current holders of the rights of *Star Trek*, allow the distribution of this fan film as long as it is not exploited for financial gain. In fact this is the only fan film entitled to use the original brand and logos in virtue of an agreement –oral, not written- with Paramount.

The main points of this oral agreement are:

1. These fan films are created for non profit use.
2. They can not be displayed in any festival, convention or other event where viewers have to pay to see it.
3. They may only be available via free download. They cannot be offered in exchange for a "donation".

4. Paramount must be properly credited as the owner of the intellectual property rights of the series.

The script for *Blood and Fire* was write for the first season of *The Next Generation*, but was rejected. In an interview for *Star Trek New Voyages e-magazine* (3rd issue) Gerrold said that a few weeks after the script was rejected:

a couple of people on the staff, who should have known better, started spreading the story that the script had been canceled because it's very good, and that I had been fired. That was a slander on my ability as a writer, and would have hurt my ability to get my work elsewhere. So I started selling copies of the script at conventions, so fans could judge themselves, and I donate the proceeds to the AIDS project of Los Angeles. Over the next 10 years, I raised about \$30,000 and apparently the script developed a certain legendary mystique (p 18)

This statement leads to a couple of conclusions: the first one is that the episode was not rejected because of low lack of quality but because of its implicit reading; on the other hand, the unfilmed script had drawn a lot of attention from the most active fandom during the years since it was first written. The script had not been accepted because it made a metaphor for AIDS and also because it portrayed with relative subtlety a relationship between two male members of the crew.

This is a standard plot in which the Enterprise goes on a mission to investigate the distress signal emitted by other ship, which is placed under quarantine because of some plasmasites called Regolian bloodworms which had caused death of a great part of its crew. Dr. Crusher believes that if the survivors were transported to her ship, they may be cured, but some of the Enterprise crew ask the captain to desist from the rescue because it may endanger their families. Undoubtedly, had it not been rejected, this episode would have been one of the most direct pieces of criticism of a contemporary phenomenon ever made in the *Star Trek* franchise.

In 2007, the people of *Phase II* addressed the project of filming the script and offered its writer, David Gerrold, the chance to direct it. The script was adapted by Carlos Pedraza, one of the contributors to this series of fan films, who made some necessary changes. To start with, the story, originally written for *Star Trek: The Next Generation* series, became an episode of *Star Trek: The Original Series*, which was even more challenging

because at the root of the '60s show was a concept of masculinity linked to heterosexuality, which means 'high-testosterone level' male characters, thus making it a little bit difficult to introduce this romance onboard the starship. Other change has to do with the relationship between these two crew members: in the original script only it was merely suggested, whereas in this new version the relationship is more explicit. The queer plot does not become an accessory plot because it directly affects the starship captain, which makes the episode more dramatic. On the other hand, the modified script conserves the main plot, including the AIDS metaphor.

What follows is an analysis of how this relationship is addressed in the first half of this two-part episode, whose second part is not available yet.

There are four scenes in this episode which enable us to analyze how a gay relationship is portrayed in a truly canonical universe:

- The first scene takes place in the starship infirmary after having been attacked by a Klingon ship. Here we see the two protagonists of the story: Peter Kirk, played by Bobby Rice, and Evan Fowler, played by Alex Freeman. The first one has been injured during the attack and Evan works in the infirmary. In this scene we can see how these characters relate to each other through their gazes and gestures. Also, Evan spends more time with Peter than with other patients. The preview of the still unreleased second part of the episode shows a similar scene, but this time Peter rejects Evan violently manner, just in a ways that shows the confidence with Evan.
- The second scene shows Peter Kirk frustrated because his uncle has not included him in a rescue mission; Evan goes tries to comfort him in his room. Here the nature of the relationship between these two characters is shown openly and unequivocally. Kisses, hugs and confidences are the protagonists of a scene presided by the intimacy shared by the couple. This scene can be seen as a manifesto against the statements of Berman and his theory against the portrayal of homosexual relationships, but then it also emphasizes that *Star Trek* is a series in which personal relationships are above anything else, a series about people as Roddenberry said. However, Peter Kirk tells Evan: "Maybe he thinks I'm here because I want to serve on his orders ... I'm here because of you." It is a

statement of intent that demonstrates the IDIC prescribes not only the relationships between people of different races but also same-sex relationships between humans.

- In the third scene Peter Kirk asks his uncle to officiate his marriage to Evan. The scene is exactly a representation on the acceptance of homosexuality in the Trek universe. The sequence is as follows: in the previous scene Captain Kirk recorded an entry about his nephew in his personal log, and now he is overprotecting him; then, Peter asks his uncle to explain to him why he has not been included in the mission, in which Evan does take part. Peter tells the captain about his relationship with Evan and asks him to officiate their marriage, which is followed by some babbling by the captain while he tries to assimilate the news. As I said, this scene can be understood as the acceptance of homosexuality in the *Star Trek* universe, for two reasons: First, because he behaves as someone who wants to be an independent person, without the overprotection of his uncle and a society that wants to ignore him. And secondly, because he decides to come out by himself, without the approval of a society embodied by the captain. That is why both the character and his sexual status are accepted within the micro-society of the starship.
- Finally, in the last scene, Peter and Evan, now in the course of the rescue mission, are having a conversation about their future marriage and their respective families. And the original scene in which a fellow asks Peter when he first met Evan, and he in a subtle way asks since when they meet each other, Peter answers that he fell in love since he met him in the Starfleet Academy.

These scenes underline how easily a homosexual relationship can be portrayed within the canon, in contradiction of the difficulties alleged by the producers of the franchise.

The second canonical example of homosexuality is *Star Trek: Hidden Frontier* (2000-2007), a fan film series of 50 episodes over seven seasons. The series, which premiered in 2000, is an offshoot of the fan series *Voyages of the USS Angeles*, produced by the Star Trek fan club of that starship. For legal reasons no copies of the earlier series are available to the public and no reference to the show is even made on the club's web site.

Episodes revolve around the starship USS Excelsior, and its home base, Deep Space 12. Two new spin-offs, *Star Trek: Odyssey* and *Star Trek: The Helena Chronicles*, both take place shortly after the end of *Hidden Frontier*. Based in the Briar Patch, a little part of the space represented in the *Star Trek* universe, introduced in *Star Trek: Insurrection* (Jonathan Frakes, 1998), this is a canonical issue that makes this series be included inside the *Star Trek* chronology, at least for the fandom. It follows the daily life of several officers serving on board the station and a few of the ships stationed there. Early in the series, an advanced species, the Grey, are introduced and become the primary villains, with a story arc that spans the entire series.

Because of the expense involved in building and storing the sets required for all the locations used in the series, it was filmed in a spare room of the executive producer's home, using green screen matting technology to place actors into virtual sets. As a result, there is often a slight green halo around the actors, but, despite its technical deficiencies, the series is remarkable for having some scripts with a quality above the average of fan films.

This series tackles homosexuality in a completely different way than what we have seen in *Blood and Fire - Part 1*. Whereas that was the typical gay episode of the season without much impact in the fictional universe, the creators of *Hidden Frontier* propose something completely novel, not just in the *Star Trek* universe, but also for the standards of any sci-fi series: a gay storyline arc that unfolds over 14 chapters encompassing 7 seasons. There are three main characters in this plot: Corey Aster, an openly gay human played by JT Tepnapa; Ro Nevin, a very religious Bajoran, not openly gay, played by Arthur Bosserman and Bobby Rice; and Jori Zen / Dao, a Trill played by Adam Browne. The choice of the characters' races is not trivial: the human embodies the social evolution of mankind in the Trek universe, but taken to the sexual sphere, his homosexuality is not limited to a minor or episodic; on the other hand, Ro Nevin is a character biased by religion, because the Bajorans are religious by definition; and thirdly, as we have seen before, the Trill come in handy when dealing with queer issues because of their gender indetermination, so uncommon within the *Star Trek* franchise.

This series portrays gay characters and their interpersonal relationships –not just of a sentimental nature- within a canon universe, as, even though the *Hidden Frontier* universe is not 100% canonical, it does use elements that fit in the chronology of the original franchise. This text uses the background of other canonical texts to create a timeline fully compatible with the original series. On the other hand, Corey Aster, the human character in the fan film, he is a specialist in terraformation, that is the processes through which lifeless planets become habitable, which makes him a unique character in the series, since this role is most often associated with spiritual characters or with women as traditional creators of life. Also, this series has gained the honor of being the first *Star Trek* production –either official or not- to show a kiss between two men, and the first one with several regular gay characters who are not there because of their sexual orientation but because, like the rest of the characters, they have a role inside the ship.

Fanonical homosexuality in *Star Trek* fan films

In this part dedicated to the re-write of homosexuality from the Fanon perspective, we enter a different area. First, these videos are made with original materials decontextualising its elements to create audiovisual narratives with entirely new meaning. Secondly, it is a field whose direct origins within the fandom production is fan fiction, namely the Slash subgenre, which Bacon-Smith, defines as follows:

Homoerotic highly romantic fiction using the characters from the source products. The term is derived from the virgule used to separate the names or initials of the two or mores characters involved in a sexual romantic relationship, and distinct from names or initials separated by a dash or an ampersand indicating only a friendship or familiar relationship. Many histories are highly romantic, some are explicitly erotic, but the presence of a sexual act in the text is not necessary for the categorization; only the implication that the action takes place in a fictional universe where such a relationship exists is needed (Bacon-Smith, 1992, pp. 314-315)

Because of the subject it treats, this kind of fan fiction is fairly popular among the fandom. Within the context of *Star Trek* stories, this is especially true for the *K/S* (Kirk/Spock) variety, also called *Spirks* (Spock and Kirk contraction) which establishes a homoerotic relationship between the main characters of the series. But, outside of that

relationship, they still have heterosexual relationships with women, just as in the original series. Most of these pieces are *songvids*, ie associations of songs –usually with a romantic and sometimes sexual meaning- to images extracted from the episodes or movies of the franchise in order to produce queer readings. The creators of these audiovisual texts have found on video portals such as YouTube an unparalleled platform for distribution and promotion. In some cases these videos creators can be qualified as authors because they have consolidated background.

Gay Pearson establishes three modes of intersection of science fiction with queer at textual level: ‘SF narrative that is not overtly queer, proto-queer an image coded as queer’ (Pearson, 2008, pp.18-19). Thus, *Star Trek* corresponds to the second mode, the proto-queer text, defined by Pearson as ‘not queer itself, effects a kind of discursive challenge to the naturalized understanding of sexuality and its concomitant social and cultural surround’ (*idem*).

The example for study is *Closer* (2006), the title of a song by Nine Inch Nails. This video created by Tjones & Killa, exploits sadomasochistic aspects of the relationship between Kirk and Spock, following the premise ‘What if they had not made it to Vulcan in time?.’ The beginning of the song lyrics reads as follows:

You let me violate you, you let me desecrate you
You let me penetrate you, you let me complicate you
Help me I broke apart my insides, help me Ive got no
Soul to tell
Help me the only thing that works for me, help me get
Away from myself
I want to fuck you like an animal
I want to feel you from the inside
I want to fuck you like an animal

This video captures the sexual tension accumulated between these two characters after repressing their desires for so long. Despite the fact that his race is governed by logic, Spock is the more violent of the two, carried away by passion until he finally rapes Kirk both mentally –via the mental merge technique- and physically. This *songvid* shows a relationship based on dependence despite Spock’s rape of Kirk. Image manipulations in the making of this video encompass not only juxtaposition, but also the application of

filters and cuts that imitate silent film effects which accentuate the violence of the relationship between the two characters. This example defines *Star Trek* as a proto-queer hypotext in which every element gives rise to a queer-coded text.

Conclusion

As we have seen, the fact that franchises are officially heterocentric does not prevent fans from calling that imperative into question within the *Star Trek* universe. In order to do so, the fans must have ‘the cultural background of a formative decision ... the worldview that it represents’ (Eco, 1985, p.197). The said knowledge of these works gives rise to a ‘variety of possible answers, this is a sign of freedom from ambiguity, the power of information specific to the proposed configuration’ (Eco, 1985, p.212). Among those responses we have the introduction of gay characters not just in an episodic pattern, but as regular characters in the series.

In the case of *songvids*, we have seen how the reinterpretation of characters and situations along with the decontextualization of music can turn a homosocial text into a homoerotic one.

As Sedgwick has written ‘the definition of one’s sexuality might be based on one’s preference for some older or younger, for a human or an animal, for a single partner or a group activity, for one self alone or for a variety of different partners’(quoted in Tyson, 2006, p.336). This is not something that happens in the canonical *Star Trek* universe, where the characters are, by definition, heterosexual; however, in the universe proposed by the fans, the characters’ sexualities are defined by their desires.

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